

Research on the early warning of academic papers based on the citations of retracted papers

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Abstract

Based on unreliable knowledge may make the study unreliable and subsequently be retracted. Retracted papers may carry unreliable knowledge, so we should pay attention to the papers that have cited the retracted papers and actively retract problematic papers to minimize their impact on academia as soon as possible. On the one hand, we can judge whether retracted papers carry unreliable knowledge by the reasons for retraction. On the other hand, we can judge whether the citing paper depends on the retracted paper by citation features. Based on these two aspects and previous study, we choose 20 features that could be used for predicting whether the citing papers are problematic and will be retracted or not. Three feature selection algorithms: Correlation-based, variance threshold and relief-F, are used to calculate the contribution of each feature. On this basis, key features that can better predict retracted papers are screened out. Four classifiers of SVM, KNN, naïve bayes and RF are used to test the classification performance of these key features. The results show that it is feasible to use citation features and reasons for retraction to predict whether the papers that have cited retracted papers will be retracted or not with high accuracy.

Keywords

Retracted Papers; Early Warning of Retracted Papers; Full-text Citation Analysis Method; Reasons for Retraction

Introduction

As we all know, research is continuous and usually based on the previous work. And citation behavior can reflect the continuity of research. But, if there are problems with previous studies, it is likely to lead to problematic studies based on them. For example, In October 2018, Harvard Medical School announced that it would retract 31 papers published by Piero Anversa, former director of the Center for Regenerative Medicine at Harvard Medical School, from several medical journals, and the entire research on cardiac stem cells was deemed "based on fraudulent data from the start", leading to the collapse of the field of "cardiac stem cells". In July 2022, Science published a six-month study, which said that Sylvain Lesne, a neuroscientist at the University of Minnesota (UMN) in the US, published more than 20 papers that may have been linked to academic misconduct, which may cause nasty effect: misleading Alzheimer's research around the world for 16 years. These events like that halfway through the construction of a skyscraper, we find that the foundation is entirely made of foam, which collapses when touched. This shows that the reliability of the research basis is very important.

The number of retracted papers has been growing in recent years. And retracted papers are seen to be cited by many papers (da Silva and Bornemann-Cimenti 2017; Hesselmann et al. 2017; Bar-Ilan and Halevi 2017a). Besides, some retracted papers may carry false knowledge and have serious negative implications not only on science but also on society (Bar-Ilan et al. 2018). da Silva and Dobr'anszki (2017) have mentioned in their study that citing retracted papers can be a problem for academia. A considerable number of papers are retracted or corrected after citing retracted papers (Yao Changqing et al. 2014; Budd et al. 2016), for example, Budd et

al.(2016) found that 16 papers have been retracted among 86 papers that have cited retracted papers. Frampton et al. (2021) found that the retracted publication of COVID-19 led to a series of restatements and corrections. Retracted papers are often retracted for their unreliable result, and if these retracted papers are used to be the research basis of others papers, which may influence the reliability of the citing paper. Generally, to find out problematic papers that have cited retracted papers, we can use full-text citation analysis method to analyze whether the cited retracted paper play an important role in the citing paper. On the other hands, not all retracted papers are unreliable, and some papers are retracted for plagiarism or duplication, which belong to ethical misconduct not scientific distortion. So, we can combine with the reasons for retraction and citation features to find out the questionable or unreliable research that have cited retracted papers.

In summary, this study will use the full-text citation analysis method and the reasons for retraction to predict whether a paper citing a retracted paper will be retracted or not. Figure 1 shows the sketch of prediction of retracted papers framework proposed in this paper.

Figure 1. The framework on predicting the citing paper citing being retracted or not

Short literature review about studies regarding the risk/probability of paper being retracted

There are few studies on the risk of paper being retracted. Some scholars (Rathmann and Rauhut, 2019; Sharma, K, 2021) have researched the correlativity of team size and retraction. Rathmann and Rauhut (2019) found that larger teams show a lower probability of having co-authored a retracted publication than smaller teams. Thus, it seems that collaboration might prevent methodological mistakes, data errors, and scientific misconduct. Sharma, K (2021) found that teams smaller in size have more retractions. Besides, Shema, Hahn et al. (2019) found that positive effects of altmetric scores and the time between publication and retraction on the probability to be retracted due to misconduct in the top sample. Robin Haunschild et al. (2020) proposed that some sources, such as blogs or post-publication peer-review sites, can be included in such an early warning system of paper being retracted. Lin Yuan et al. (2021) used the questioning data raised by others on PubPeer to warn high-risk authors. Lingzi Feng (2022) calculated the risk of paper retraction from three levels of author, paper and journal, and established a set of paper retraction risk early warning mechanism. But little studies have paid attention to the correlativity of citing retracted papers and retraction, and the risk of retraction due to citing retracted paper.

Method

Constructing the feature space

We are concerned with a binary classification problem: Given citing papers that have cited retracted papers, classify them as either retracted papers or not retracted papers. The task is to create a model that takes a pair, consisting of a given citing paper (the citing paper) and some retracted reference in the given paper (the cited paper), as input, and generate a label (retracted or not retracted) as output. Our goal is to create a model that can predict the labels assigned by database publishers in our gold-standard data set. Our approach to this task is to use supervised machine learning. For supervised machine learning, we must generate feature vectors that represent a variety of properties of each citing paper and retracted reference pair. Given a training set of manually labelled citing paper, a learning algorithm can create a model for predicting the label of the citing paper in the testing set. We use some standard supervised machine learning algorithm in our experiments: support vector machine, naïve bayes, random forest and KNN. The main contribution of this paper is that we evaluate a wide range of different features for representing the citing paper and retracted references pairs. Finding good features is the key to successful prediction. In our experiments, we consider the following 20 features shown in table 1. And these features have been used to test the citation function in different area, such as computer science, biology, physics and chemistry disciplines (Pak et al. 2018).

Table 1. 20 features to predict whether the paper will be retracted

<i>Features</i>	<i>Detailed information</i>
F1	Self-citation
F2	Same first or corresponding author
F3	Mentioned position in discussion
F4	Mentioned position in result
F5	Mentioned position in method
F6	Mentioned position in experiment
F7	Mentioned position in introduction
F8	Mentioned position in else
F9	Mentioned polarity in positive
F10	Mentioned polarity negative
F11	Mentioned polarity neutral
F12	Retracted papers' mentioned frequency in the citing papers
F13	The number of cited retracted papers in the references of the citing papers
F14	The proportion of retracted papers in the references of the citing papers
F15	The similarity of the title between the cited retracted papers and the citing papers
F16	The similarity of the abstracts between the cited retracted papers and the citing papers
F17	The number of mentioned alone of the cited retracted papers
F18	Citation sentence length
F19	Unreliable reasons
F20	The number of unreliable reasons

Not all of these features are useful. However, many of these features are intuitively attractive, and we can only find out if (and the extent to which) they are useful through experiments. We describe these features in the following subsections.

Self-citation and same first or corresponding author

We believe that the researchers' fraudulent behavior is not accidental. It's a habitual behavior and the researchers may consistently change or falsify data in multiple articles, resulting in unreliable results. And we think if the author of the citing paper is same to the author of the cited retracted paper, the citing paper may be problematic. So, the first feature is used to judge whether there is a shared author between the citation pair. If there's shared author in the citation pair, $F1=1$. Otherwise, $F1=0$. Usually, first author and corresponding author play more important role in the research. So, we think if the first or corresponding author is same in the citation pair, $F2=1$. Otherwise, $F2=0$.

Mentioned position

Wang et al. (2020) show in their study that the citations in the introduction and literature review are usually used to lay the foundation for new research; the citations in the methods and experiments are used to support the design and implementation of methods. Gibson (2021) found that misconduct behaviours related to data is more likely to accept punishment. So, mentioned position can characterize the role that references play in the citing paper, and it can be used to judge the reliability of the citing paper. In this study, F3-F8 are used to examine the location of the citation in the citing papers. And we use the first title to label the location of the citation. If the citation sentence occurs in the introduction, we will label its location introduction. And combining with the article structure of the data source that we choose, we divide the position into 6 kinds: discussion, result, method, experiment, introduction and else position. Finally, we calculate the occurrence number of citation in different position.

Mentioned polarity

These features (F9-F11) describe the emotional tendency of the author to the cited retracted papers. For the recognition of sentiment components in citation sentences, we invoke the `nlptown/bert-base-multilingual-uncased-sentiment` and the accuracy rate on the test set was 91%. And we divided the citation polarity into three categories of positive, negative and neutral, and identified the author's emotional tendency in each citation segment. The number of citation segments with different emotional polarity was counted, and the value of each citation polarity index was assigned accordingly. For example, if the cited retracted paper PA were cited three times by its citing literature PB, two of which are positive citations and one is a negative citation, then we got: $F9=2$, $F10=1$, $F11=0$. All the collected features are normalized to the interval [0.01, 0.99] to ensure the uniformity of the indices' value range.

Mentioned frequency

Mentioned frequency is an important indicator of citation value, which can show the information of how the cited papers are used in citing papers in more detail (Hu et al. 2015; Pak et al. 2018; Wang et al. 2019c, Wang et al., 2020). So, we think if the cited retracted papers are mentioned more times, the citing paper is more dependent on the cited retracted paper. And if the cited retracted papers are unreliable, the citing paper are high likely to be unreliable. This feature (F12) is used to represent the number of citations that the cited retracted papers are mentioned in the citing paper.

Number and proportion of retracted references

F13 is used to represent the number of retracted papers in the references of the citing papers. but considering that different papers have different numbers of references, we also choose the proportion of retracted papers in the references of the citing papers (F14). Usually, if the number and proportion of retracted references is higher, the citing paper is more likely to be unreliable.

Similarity of cited retracted papers and the corresponding citing papers

These features (F15-F16) are used to examine the theme similarity between citation pairs. This paper calculated the text similarity of citation pair according to the title and abstract of the citation pair. Usually, the higher the theme similarity is between citation pairs, the more likely the paper is to rely on the cite retracted papers. And we use the deep learning model of “Sentence_Transformer (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019)” to calculated the similarity of titles and abstracts. The model is evaluated extensively on 15+ datasets including challenging domains like Tweets, Reddit, emails. They achieve by far the best performance from all available sentence embedding methods. And the final values are between 0 and 1.

Mentioned alone

Hu et al (2015) calculated the Pearson’s correlation coefficient between important citation and enumeration rate (mentioned together with other references), it is found that there is a weak negative correlation between them. And this can be used in the citation to retracted papers, too, if the retracted papers are mentioned together with other references, it may show that the cited retracted papers are not important in the citing paper. Conversely, if the retracted papers are mentioned alone in the citing paper, it may play more important role. So, we use F17 to represent the occurrence number of the retracted papers mentioned alone in the citing papers. And the feature is normalized to the interval [0.01, 0.99] to ensure the uniformity of the indices’ value range.

Citation sentence length

Tang and Safer (2008) proposed that the more sentences describing a cited work in citing literature, the more important the cited work is to the citing work. the number of words in the citation sentence. It can be used in the citation to retracted papers, too. If the citation sentence includes more words, the cited retracted papers may play more important role in the citing paper. F18 is used to describe the citation sentence length, and that's how many words are in the citation sentence.

Reasons for retraction

There are multiple reasons behind retracted papers including duplicate publication, falsification of the data, fabrication of the data, ethical or legal misconduct, etc. (Steen et al., 2013; Bohannon, 2016). Bar-Ilan, J. and Halevi, G. (2018) categorized reasons for retraction into three categories: (1) ethical misconduct (e.g. duplicate publication, plagiarism, missing credit, no IRB, ownership issues, authorship issues, interference in the review process, citation manipulation); (2) scientific distortion (e.g. data manipulation, fraudulent data, unsupported conclusions, questionable data validity, non-replicability, data errors—even if unintended); (3) administrative error (e.g. article published in wrong issue, not the final version published, publisher errors). And they mentioned in their study that the retracted papers belonging to the second category are most troublesome from the scientific point of view, as they are misleading and have serious negative implications not only on science but also on society.

As the retraction phenomenon has attracted more and more attention, Retraction Watch, a platform dedicated to tracking the disclosure of retracted papers, was established in 2010. In October 2018, Retraction Watch Database was officially launched and opened to scholars and the public free of charge. It has included most retracted papers so far. The database structurally labels the reasons for retractions descriptively according to each publication's retractions statement, with 103 reasons By December 2022.

On the basis of the existing results, we think the following reasons for retraction in the Retraction Watch Database that belong to scientific distortion and can show whether the retracted paper is unreliable or not.

- Concerns/Issues About Data
- Concerns/Issues About Image
- Concerns/Issues About Results
- Error in Analyses
- Error in Cell Lines/Tissues
- Error in Data
- Error in Image
- Falsification/Fabrication of Data
- Falsification/Fabrication of Image
- Falsification/Fabrication of Results
- Manipulation of Images
- Manipulation of Results
- Error in Materials (General)
- Error in Methods
- Error in Results and/or Conclusions
- Error in Text
- Unreliable Data
- Unreliable Image
- Unreliable Results

So F19 is used to show whether the reason of retraction of the cited retracted papers include the above reasons. And F20 is used to count the number of above reasons.

Feature selection

These feature selection methods are the simplest but can be very useful in supervised machine learning: correlation-based feature selection method, variance threshold feature selection method and the Relief-F algorithm.

Correlation-based

To measure every feature's correlation with the retraction label, this study uses Pearson's correlation coefficient to calculate the correlation coefficient between every feature and retraction label. The Pearson correlation coefficients between the various features and the gold influence labels are a simple indication of how useful a feature might be (Zhu et al. 2015; Wang et al. 2020). So, we use Pearson's correlation coefficient to assess all features' relevance to the retraction label, too. And Chi-square test is often used to verify the correlation between the grouped data that can be described by two or more categories, which can be used in self_citation, same first or corresponding author and unreliable reasons features in this study.

Relief-F

The Relief-F algorithm was first proposed by Kira and Rendell (1992) to calculate the weight of features in binary classification problems. The basic idea of Relief-F is to draw instances at random, compute their nearest neighbors, and adjust a feature weighting vector to give larger weight to features that can well discriminate the instances from neighbors of different classes (Kononenko 1994).

Variance threshold

Using variance threshold method, the variance of each feature should be calculated first, and then according to the threshold value, the feature with variance greater than the threshold value should be selected.

Classification process

In this paper, four classifiers of support vector machine (SVM), KNN, Naïve Bayes and random forest (RF) are used to test the classification performance of the proposed classification framework.

SVM

SVM is a kind of generalized linear classifier, which classifies the data according to the supervised learning method. Its decision boundary is the maximum margin hyperplane for learning samples. The support vector machine model based on radial kernel function is a widely used classifier (Hernández-Álvarez et al. 2016), which is used in the current work to perform the classification process.

KNN

KNN is a classification algorithm based on distance measurement. In the learning process, KNN takes the whole data set as the training set. Based on a given distance measure, KNN finds the k training samples which are closest to the sample to be classified, and generates classification results based on the information of these k nearest “neighbours”. The “voting method” is generally used in the classification task, that is, the most frequent category in the k nearest “neighbours” is selected as the final category to the sample to be classified. In this study, we use the distance weighted KNN proposed by Dudani (1976) to perform the classification process.

Naïve Bayes

Naive Bayes is a kind of model in Bayesian classifier. The model is trained with the data set of known classes, so as to realize the class judgment of the unknown class data. The theory is based on Bayesian decision theory.

Random Forest (RF)

Random forest is an integrated classifier using multiple decision trees for training and prediction (Breiman 2001). It consists of a group of decision trees, each decision tree is taken as a base classifier, and the final classification result is determined by the majority vote, just like the KNN algorithm. In this study, the number of decision trees in a random forest is set to 42.

Evaluation index of binary classification problem

The commonly used evaluation indicators for two-class classification problems are precision, recall, and F1 score. And there are some basic concepts:

- TP: the number of predicting the positive class as positive classes
- FN: the number of predicting positive classes as negative classes
- FP: the number of predicting negative classes as positive classes
- TN: the number of predicting negative classes as negative classes
- T: the number of actual positive classes
- F: the number of actual negative classes

Accuracy

Accuracy is calculated as the number of data correctly classified by the algorithm divided by the number of data entered into the algorithm:

$$A=(TP+TN)/(T+F) \quad (1)$$

Precision

Precision is the proportion of samples predicted to be positive over all positive samples:

$$P=TP/(TP+FP) \quad (2)$$

Recall

Recall is the proportion of correctly predicted data in the total sample:

$$R=TP/(TP+FN)=TP/T \quad (3)$$

F1 score

The F1 score, which is a balanced index of precision and recall, is the harmonic average of precision and recall:

$$F1=2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall} / (\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}) \quad (3)$$

And in this study, for different classifiers, we use different accuracy. For all classifiers, we use accuracy to compare their performance. And for RF, we use precision, recall, F1-score.

Experimental results and discussion

Data Set

We choose Web of Science (WOS) Database as this study's data source, because WOS has collected and labelled many retracted papers. Besides, it offers citation report function, which allows us to acquire the references and citing papers of the retracted papers. And we choose the retracted papers and the citing papers published on the Journal of Biology Chemistry. There are three reasons. The first is that the life science field has always been the field with a largest number of retracted papers, and further research on retracted papers in this area is warranted. And in the journal articles included in the WOS database, the number of retracted papers published on Journal of Biology Chemistry ranked first. The second is that papers published on the Journal of Biology Chemistry is open access. The last reason is that the structure of these papers is similar to each other, which is good for labelling some features, like the position that the cited retracted papers occur in the paper. The data acquisition process and research design are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The data acquisition process and research design

Although we choose the data in life science field, we find the phenomenon exists in many disciplines. In the WOS database, more than 42 retracted papers have cited retracted papers in psychology discipline. And more than 142 retracted papers have cited retracted papers in computer science discipline.

Feature selection result

Usually, if the Pearson's correlation coefficient is more than 0.2, we can think the independent variable and the dependent variable are correlated. And if the Pearson's correlation coefficient is more than 0.4, we can think they are moderately correlated. And if it is more than 0.6, we can think they are strong correlated. As shown in Table 2, in the correlation coefficients between the features and the retraction labels, F1 and F2 are strong correlated to the retraction label. Next, F6 and F17 are moderate correlated to the retraction label. Besides, F3, F7, F9, F11, F12, F13, F14, F15, F16, F18 and F20 is weak correlated with retraction label.

Table 2. The feature selection result according to Pearson, Relief-F and Variance

Feature	Pearson	Relief-F	Variance	Feature	Pearson	Relief-F	Variance
F1	0.65	0.65	☑	F11	0.32	0.00	/
F2	0.75	0.77	☑	F12	0.39	0.00	/
F3	0.23	0.00	/	F13	0.32	-0.01	/
F4	0.16	-0.01	/	F14	0.27	-0.02	/
F5	0.13	0.00	/	F15	0.24	0.01	/
F6	0.42	0.00	/	F16	0.20	0.02	/
F7	0.29	-0.01	/	F17	0.43	0.00	/
F8	-0.03	0.01	/	F18	0.28	-0.01	/
F9	0.39	0.01	/	F19	0.17	0.01	/
F10	0.02	0.00	/	F20	0.22	-0.01	/

And we calculate the Pearson, Kendall and Spearman correlation coefficient of every feature and retraction label, and the results are shown in the figure 3. And they are consistent. F1 and F2 play more important role than other features.

So, in the experiment part, we intend to set up three experimental groups: (1) all features; (2) F1 and F2; (3) F1, F2, F6, and F17; (4) all correlative features exclude F4, F5, F8, F10 and F19. Besides, to examine whether features associated with reasons for retraction play a role or not, we set another experimental group: (5) all features excluding F19 and F20.

Figure 3-1 Pearson

Figure 3-2 Kendall

Figure 3-3 Spearman

Figure 3. The correlation coefficient between every feature and retraction.

In this study, some features can be divided into two or more categories, so we also use Chi-square test to assess the degree of correlation with retraction label. The results are displayed in the table 3. Usually, if the p-value is less than 0.05, the two variables are considered to be significantly correlated. So, self_citation and same first or corresponding author are related to retraction label, which is consistent with the Pearson's correlation coefficient's result. According to results of the chi-square test, the unreliable reasons feature is related to retraction label, too, which is not consistent with the Pearson's correlation coefficient's result. So, in the experiment part, we plan to compare the performance of prediction with and without this feature.

Table 3. results of the chi-square test between three features and retraction.

<i>Feature</i>	<i>Chi-square value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Degrees of freedom</i>
Self_citation	129.9	<0.001	1
Same first or corresponding author	175.2	<0.001	1
Unreliable reasons	8.32	0.004	1

And after using relief-f and variance feature selection methods, which is shown in table 2, we find that F1 and F2 may play the most important role among these features. So, in the experiment part, we plan to examine the performance of prediction only with these two features.

Experimental results

The classification accuracy of each algorithm according to different features is shown in figure 4. We can find that all four classifiers perform well. KNN is more sensitive to the number of correlative features. If there are unrelated features mixed in, the performance of KNN will reduce. Naïve bayes performs best than other classifiers. In the experiment process, we find the prediction accuracy of RF is relatively consistent compared with other classifiers. As for other classifiers, their accuracy often fluctuates up and down, but it is almost above 0.8. So, we further compared the evaluation indexes of RF, the result is shown in table 5 and table 6. And the overall performance is good, and the performance is better with more feature.

Figure 4. Classification accuracy of each algorithm according to different features

Table 5. Classification performance of random forest according to F1-F20 features

	<i>precision</i>	<i>recall</i>	<i>F1-score</i>
Retracted	0.75	0.86	0.80
Not retracted	0.96	0.92	0.94

Table 6. Classification performance of random forest according to F1-F18 features

	<i>precision</i>	<i>recall</i>	<i>F1-score</i>
Retracted	0.64	1	0.78
Not retracted	1	0.84	0.91

Conclusions

The results show that it is feasible to use citation features and reasons for retraction to predict whether the papers that have cited retracted papers will be retracted or not, and it is with high accuracy. The contributions of this paper are mainly in two aspects: (1) This is the first time to introduce citation behaviours into academic paper early warning. And the framework proposed in this paper comprehensively examines the syntactic features brought about by citation behaviours and the contextual features brought about by citation context. (2) The early warning framework proposed in this study does work. And the method proposed in this study can be used to identify problematic papers early for the academic journals and publishers.

Limitations and future work

Firstly, in this study we only choose retracted papers and its citing papers published on the Journal of Biology Chemistry as data source. In the future, we can use more retracted papers to verify the reliability of the prediction algorithm. Secondly, in this study we do not make a more detailed analysis of the reasons for retraction. In the future, we can compare whether the retraction rate is different among citing papers, which have cited papers retracted for different reasons. For example, if the paper is more likely to be retracted for citing the paper retracted for unreliable result. Finally, the lack of adequate performance tuning for the various classification algorithms is also a drawback of this study. In the future, when we use more data, we can train a better model.

Acknowledgments

We thank Lixue, Wang from the National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences for his data cleaning work. We thank Ruhao, Zhang from the National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences for his help about the recognition of sentiment components in citation sentences. We thank Yang, Zhao from the National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences for her important suggestions. This work is supported by the Research on Journal Ranking Method Between Chinese and Foreign Academic Citation Systems (NSSFC: 19BTQ090).

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